

Description of scurvy by Ronsseus (1564)

Summary by James Lind (1753)

In the 16th century, four European authors described the symptoms of scurvy in such a detail that the disease can be recognized as the disease we currently classify as scurvy: *Echtius* (1541), *Olaus Magnus* (1555), *Ronsseus* (1564), and *Wierus* (1567). Since these four texts are among the early unambiguous descriptions of scurvy, they have substantial historical relevance. All these texts were originally published in Latin. There are English translations of the sections of scurvy from the Olaus Magnus text. James Lind wrote English summaries of the texts of the three other authors. This document gives a brief background and a copy of Lind's summary of Ronsseus (1564) text on scurvy.

Various names of the author (1525–1597):

Ronsseus

Balduinus Ronsseus

Boudewijn Ronsse

https://nl.wikipedia.org/wiki/Boudewijn_Ronsse in Dutch

Yellow is used to indicate the description of symptoms of scurvy.

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Background

*James Lind (1753)*¹ wrote, p.1

In the first accounts given us of this disease, by **Ronsseus**², **Echthius**³, and **Wierus**⁴ (a), it is surprising to find, not only an accurate description of it, but an enumeration of almost all the truly antiscorbutic medicines that are known to the world even at this day.

(a) The first authors on the scurvy, *Ronsseus* and *Echthius*, though cotemporary, wrote separately, without having *the benefit of seeing each others works*.

James Lind p.2

Ronsseus, who believed it to be the same disease that is described by *Pliny*, and is said to have afflicted the *Roman* army under the command of *Cesar Germanicus*, observed, that in his time it was to be met with only in *Holland*, *Friesland*, and *Denmark*; though he had heard of its appearing in *Flanders*, *Brabant*, and some parts of *Germany*. From seeing some of those countries entirely free from this distemper, he was induced to ascribe its frequency in other places to their soil, climate, and diet. In order to prove which, he wrote his first epistle.

James Lind p.125

Moisture was discovered to be one of the causes of this malady by *Ronsseus*, the very first author who ever wrote expressly upon it.

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- 1 James Lind (1753). A Treatise of the Scurvy in Three Parts. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685194> Selected sections of Lind's treatise. Lind's 1753 edition in a scanned versions: <https://wellcomecollection.org/works/bg2gxrzz/items?canvas=7> <https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/xvi/mode/2up> <https://library.si.edu/digital-library/book/treatisescurvyt00lind>
 - 2 Ronsseus, see: Lind. Part III: Chapter II. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093314> <https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/356/mode/2up>
 - 3 Echthius, see: Lind. Part III: Chapter II. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093279> <https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/354/mode/2up>
 - 4 Wierus, see: Lind. Part III: Chapter II. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093229> <https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/358/mode/2up>

James Lind p.131-132

Thus, *Ronsseus* takes notice, that in his time it was a much more frequent malady at *Amsterdam* and *Alomaer*, than at *Goude* and *Rotterdam*; and at *Dort*, though in the same climate, and where the inhabitants eat the same food, it was hardly ever to be seen: but that, universally, in all parts of the country where the soil was senny, damp, and marshy, it raged with the greatest violence. This very accurate author observes likewise, the great influence which the weather had upon it; as, that along continuance of southerly and westerly winds always occasioned a great frequency of this distress; but that rainy seasons especially, rendered the mischief quite epidemic and malignant. When this physician wrote, his country was little better than a large morass, exposed to frequent inundations from floods and high tides; which, together with the gross coarse diet used by the *Dutch* at that time, made the scurvy perhaps the most frequent endemic of their country. But now they are become a rich flourishing republic, and have dried and improved their soil by dikes and drains, and also quite altered their way of living, the disease appears but seldom; and is to be seen chiefly among the poorer sort, who inhabit the low damp parts of the provinces, and continue in their old gross way of living, upon salt, smoked, often rancid pork, coarse bread; and are necessitated to drink unwholsome stagnating waters. They have indeed at times been subject to violent returns of their old distemper; as in several of their wars, when obliged to overflow their country with water.

James Lind p.204-205

But these fruits have this peculiar advantage above any thing that can be proposed for trial, that their experienced virtues have stood the test of near 200 years. They were providentially discovered, even before the disease was well known, or at least had been described by physicians. *Ronsseus*, the first

writer on this subject, mentions them; and observes, that in all probability the *Dutch* sailors had by accident fallen upon this remedy, when afflicted with the scurvy, in their return from Spain loaded with these fruits, especially oranges. Experience soon taught them, that by thus eating part of their cargo, they might be restored to health.

James Lind p.352-355:

... The author afterwards observes it to be the scurvy, a malady to which the northern nations, the Dutch, &c. are very subject; and upon this occasion, quoting a passage from *Olaus Magnus*⁵, says, “I have delighted myself to recite the words of this author, because he speaketh thereof as being skilled, and has well described the disease; only he maketh no mention of the stiffening of the hams, nor of the superfluous flesh which groweth in the mouth.”

...

Olaus Magnus, in his history of the northern nations, published *ann.* 1555, observing what diseases are peculiar to them, gives us a long description of the scurvy.

...

Soon after we find three eminent physicians, all cotemporary, treating expressly of this distemper, *viz.*

Ronsseus, *Echthius*, and *Wierus*. To whom *Langius* may be added as a fourth, having wrote two epistles upon this subject. What is called *Echthius's Epitome*, was the first wrote, though the last published. It would appear from *Forrestus* to be a letter sent, in the year 1541, to *Blienburchius*, a physician at *Utrecht*; whose answer is now lost. The first book published expressly upon the scurvy was by *Ronsseus*, in the form of an epistle. The year is uncertain, as he afterwards corrected, and reprinted it in a different form. He is so modest as to say, that had he first seen *Wierus's* accurate observations, he would not have published any thing upon the subject. There is an edition of *Ronsseus* put down by *Mercklin* and *Lipenius*, in the year 1564; and of *Wierus's* observations in 1567. The learned Dr *Astruc*

5 *Olaus Magnus* (1555) *Historia de gentibus septentrionalibus*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13380745> English translation of the sections on scurvy
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/A_Description_of_the_Northern_Peoples
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Olaus_Magnus

is of opinion, that these last were not published till 1580. It is thus far certain, that those authors corresponded together; and upon *Wierus* sending to *Ronsseus*, *Echthius*'s letter, now called his *Epitome*, he published

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it, together with his own work, *Wierus*'s observations, and two of *Langius*'s epistles, in the year 1583.

James Lind p.445, Appendix

It has been no easy matter to obtain a knowledge of the many writings on this distemper. There have been collections made from time to time, of the several authors on the plague, venereal disease, &c. but no such have been compiled of writers on the scurvy. *Sennertus*, *ann.* 1624, when he wrote his own treatise, reprinted the writings of *Solomon Albertus* and *Martini*, together with *Ronsseus*, and the authors which he had published *ann.* 1583, *viz.* *Echthius*, *Wierus*, and *Langius*; and this book, containing those seven authors, is the only collection ever published of writers on the scurvy. There was here as little assistance to be obtained from medical *bibliothecæ*.

August Hirsch (1885)⁶ wrote, p.513:

Of somewhat later date are the first authentic accounts of the epidemic occurrence of scurvy on land... Shortly after there appeared the statements of **Olaus Magnus**, concerning the often observed epidemic prevalence of scurvy in the Scandinavian kingdoms, especially in times of famine; and about the same time, or a little later, the writings of **Echthius, Ronsseus, Wier, Dodonaeus** and **Brucaeus**, which testify to the comparatively common occurrence of the disease along the littoral of the North Sea and the Baltic...

These excellent descriptions of the malady, more especially by **Echthius, Ronsseus** and **Wier**, leave no doubt as to its nature [as scurvy].

Alfred Hess (1920)⁷ wrote, p.1-4:

It is probable that scurvy existed in the northern parts of Europe and Asia ever since they were settled by man. We should hardly expect to have records of this condition, in view of the low educational status of the people, their greatly restricted literature, and their lack of intercourse with the people in the southern countries. In the sixteenth century, with the development and spread of education, we begin to hear of scurvy from various sources. **Olaus Magnus**, in his "History of the Northern Nations," published in 1555, described the disease which he tells us flourished among the soldiers in the camps and in the prisons.

About this time **Ronsseus, Echthius** and **Wierus** wrote special treatises on this disease, and recommended many dietary measures which we recognize to-day as most efficacious. The number of monographs on this subject multiplied with great rapidity in the course of the next twenty-five or fifty years; none of them, however, added anything essential to our knowledge...

6 Hirsch A (1885) Handbook of Geographical and Historical Pathology. Vol. II. Scurvy: pp.507-568.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10104179> Section on scurvy separately
<https://archive.org/details/handbookofgeogra02hirsuoft/page/512/mode/2up>
https://archive.org/details/b28147455_0002/page/512/mode/2up
<https://archive.org/details/handbookofgeogra02unse/page/512/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/handbookofgeogra02hirs/page/512/mode/2up>

7 Hess AF (1920) Scurvy: Past and Present.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685195> Extracts relevant to the current context
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/40505>
<https://digital.library.cornell.edu/catalog/chla2903792>

Anthony J Lorenz (1953)⁸ wrote:

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Lind makes the Dutch physician, **Balduin Ronsseus**, *facile princeps*⁹. Ronsseus¹⁰ suggests that cold damp air of the sea and the seashore is the principal cause of scurvy. His is the first book written expressly on scurvy and was published in 1564. A later edition of Ronsseus (1585) combined the *epistolae* of **Echthius**¹¹ and Langius as well as the *observatio* of Wierus as a sort of compendium of the current views on scurvy. Ronsseus also held to the theory of involvement of the spleen in scurvy. Both Ronsseus and Echthius, writing separately, interpreted Pliny's description of the disease, which afflicted the Roman army under Germanicus, as scurvy.

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Wier (Wierus) (1567)¹², copying Echthius, and Bruner (Brunerus) (1589), copying Wierus (adding only that leg pains preceded the actual onset of scurvy) well might have justified the subhead in Lind's preface *Dies Diem Docet*¹³, and the words:

“To know a disease and to cure it being the utmost essential things to be learned, I have, therefore, transcribed the symptoms and the cure of the scurvy from those authors where they do not entirely copy from each other. I hope such motives (truth, and good of mankind) will to the candid and to the most judicious be a sufficient apology for the liberties I have assumed”.

In re-reading the principal pre-Lind authors *seriatim* one observes the transitions from land to sea scurvy, or *purpura nautica*. One also sees the transition of the concept of scurvy as a winter epidemic among urban populations and its entity as a deficiency disease when studied in the isolation of the sailing ship when voyages of discovery increased in duration sufficient to permit complete deprivation of antiscorbutic stores.

8 <https://doi.org/10.1079/PNS19530062>

9 Facile princeps. Acknowledged leader.

10 Ronsseus, B. (1585). *De Magnis Hippocratis lienibits Plinique stomachace ac sceletyrbe, seu vulgo dicto scorbuto commentariolus. Accessere q'usdem epistolae quinque ejusdem argumenti, Joannis Echthii de scorbuto epitome, Joannis Wieri de scorbuto observatio. Joanna's Langii epistolae duae de scorbuto*. Wittenberg: C. Schleich.

11 Echthius, J. (1541). *De Scorbuto, vel Scorbutica Passione Epitome*. Cologne.

12 Wier (Wierus) J. (1567). *Medicarum Observationum Rararum Liber (I de Scorbuto)*. Basle: J. Oporinus.

13 Dies Diem Docet. The day teaches the day; one learns by experience.

The text on the following pages is the summary by Lind (1753, 1st ed.) p.357-361

<https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/356/mode/2up>

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/bg2gxrzz/items?canvas=379>

Although Lind states that Ronsseus properly describes the symptoms of scurvy, in a similar way as Echthius and Wierus, Lind does not extract the symptoms that Ronsseus had described.

Balduin. Ronfeus, ordinary physician to the city of Goude in Holland.

Original in Latin:

“Balduini Ronssei Gandensis De Magnis Hippocratis Lienibus, Pliniique stomachase ac sceletyrbe, seu vulgò dicto scorbuto commentarius. Ejusdem epistolae quinque, eisdem argumenti”, p.139-180.

<https://archive.org/details/descorbutotracta00senn/page/138/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/hin-wel-all-00002888-001/page/n8/mode/2up>

https://www.google.com/books/edition/De_scorbuto_tractatus/W7w_AAAAcAAJ

<https://books.google.com/books?id=rUepnWJ1zVwC>

https://www.google.com/books/edition/De_scorbuto_tractatus_Acc_ejusdem_argume/f2RWAAAAcAAJ

A.D.1564

*Balduini Ronssei de magnis Hippocratis lienibus,
Pliniique stomachace ac sceletyrbe,
seu vulgò dicto scorbuto commentarius.
Ejusdem epistolæ quinque ejusdem argumenti.*

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He ascribes the frequency of the scurvy in *Holland* to their diet and air; to their eating great quantities of water-fowl; but principally to their living on flesh, first salted, then smoked and dried. The weather, he says, had a very great influence upon this distemper. For though it was met with in the country at all seasons; yet, by long observation and experience, he had found, that a moist air, and southerly winds, contributed greatly to increase it: and instances in the year 1556, when, during that whole year, they had almost continual rains, with southerly and westerly winds; which were followed by a great frequency of this disease; and to such a height, that many were brought in danger of their lives by it. In 1562, after a very rainy season, there likewise ensued frequent and very troublesome scurvies. So that although this malady was at all times endemic with them, from the peculiar air of the country, and their bad waters; yet, upon very slight occasions, it often became more general or epidemical during a moist season. It usually prevailed most in spring and autumn; was milder in the spring, and shorter: but in the autumn, it was of longer continuance, and more obstinate, so as sometimes to endanger the life of the patient. No age was exempted from its attack; which, though severest with old people, yet was more incident to those of a middle age.

From a mistaken theory in judging it a disease of the

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spleen, he begins the cure by bleeding. He afterwards prescribes an aperient and attenuating decoction of a number of antiscorbutics, with the addition of *senna*, and some other purgative ingredients: but observing, that the more simple compositions were generally the most efficacious, he thinks, that the use of scurvygrass, wormwood, and germander, is alone sufficient; the vulgar curing themselves by scurvygrass, brooklime, and water cresses. At the end of the cure, he gives gentle physic; forbidding

all violent and acrid medicines, especially drastic purgatives; till towards the decline of the malady, when the patient is able to bear them. For twelve years past, he had used with great success, both for prevention and cure, a tincture, in spirit of wine, of *fumaria*, *cochlearia*, *absinthium*, and *chamædry*s, or herbs of the like virtue. The spirit was extremely well saturated by repeated infusions of the fresh plants, and **the belly kept moderately open during the course**.¹⁴

As to diet, upon which much depends; he orders it should be inciding and attenuating. They must abstain from all kind of sea and water fowls; from pork, and salt meats. Their drink should be a wormwood and germander wine by turns. He prescribes a gargarism with alum and honey **for the mouth**; and orders **the rigid tendons in the ham**, after friction, to be anointed with cowfeet jelly. He has several remedies for the **ulcers on the legs**. To prevent the disease, he recommends gentle physic in the autumn; but especially the use of a light wormwood ale or wine: by which (with the help of a diet of easy digestion, the benefit of good air, and dry lodgings) he has known it often not only prevented, but cured.

In his first epistle, he accounts for the frequency of this distemper in some places more than in others; from their different soils, climates, and weather, and especially from the quality of the waters they used: and observes, that, universally, in marshy and boggy countries, people were

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most afflicted with the scurvy; though their diet and other circumstances were alike with others. In his second epistle, he maintains, that this distemper was known to the ancients, against the opinion of *Wierus*; and remarks, that seamen in long voyages cure themselves of it by the use of **oranges**. In his third epistle, he recommends the steel and mineral waters.

14 Constipation is often described as a symptom of scurvy.